

Novel Hybrid Approaches For Real Coded Genetic Algorithm To Compute The Optimal Control Of A Single Stage Hybrid Manufacturing Systems

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Abstract— This paper presents a novel two-phase hybrid optimization algorithm with hybrid genetic operators to solve the optimal control problem of a single stage hybrid manufacturing system. The proposed hybrid real coded genetic algorithm (HRCGA) is developed in such a way that a simple real coded GA acts as a base level search, which makes a quick decision to direct the search towards the optimal region, and a local search method is next employed to do fine tuning. The hybrid genetic operators involved in the proposed algorithm improve both the quality of the solution and convergence speed. The phase-1 uses conventional real coded genetic algorithm (RCGA), while optimisation by direct search and systematic reduction of the size of search region is employed in the phase - 2. A typical numerical example of an optimal control problem with the number of jobs varying from 10 to 50 is included to illustrate the efficacy of the proposed algorithm. Several statistical analyses are done to compare the validity of the proposed algorithm with the conventional RCGA and PSO techniques. Hypothesis t - test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) test are also carried out to validate the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm. The results clearly demonstrate that the proposed algorithm not only improves the quality but also is more efficient in converging to the optimal value faster. They can outperform the conventional real coded GA (RCGA) and the efficient particle swarm optimisation (PSO) algorithm in quality of the optimal solution and also in terms of convergence to the actual optimum value.

Keywords— Hybrid systems, optimal control, real coded genetic algorithm (RCGA), Particle swarm optimization (PSO), Hybrid real coded GA (HRCGA), and Hybrid genetic operators.

I. INTRODUCTION

The hybrid systems of interest contain two different types of categories: subsystems with continuous dynamics and subsystems with discrete dynamics that interact with each

other. Such hybrid systems arise in varied contexts in manufacturing, communication networks, automotive engine design, computer synchronization, and chemical processes, among others.

In hybrid manufacturing systems, the manufacturing process is composed of the event-driven dynamics of the parts moving among different machines and the time-driven dynamics of the processes within particular machines. Frequently in hybrid systems, the event-driven dynamics are studied separately from the time-driven dynamics, the former via automata or Petri net models, PLC etc., and the latter via differential or difference equations. Two categories of modeling framework have been proposed to study hybrid systems: those that extend event-driven models to include time-driven dynamics; and those that extend the traditional time-driven models to include event-driven dynamics. The hybrid system-modeling framework considered in this research falls into the first category. It is motivated by the structure of many manufacturing systems. To represent the hybrid nature of the model, each job is characterized by a *physical state* and a *temporal state*. The physical state represents the physical characteristics of interest and evolves according to the time-driven dynamics (e.g., difference or differential equations) while a server is processing the job. The temporal state represents processing arrival and completion times and evolves according to the discrete-event dynamics (e.g., queuing dynamics). The interaction of time-driven with event-driven dynamics leads to a natural tradeoff between temporal requirements on job completion times and physical requirements on the quality of the completed jobs (Fig 1). Such modeling frameworks and optimal control problems have been considered in [1,2].

Several algorithms were developed for solving such problems. In our earlier work, we proposed real coded genetic algorithms (RCGA) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithms for solving the optimal control problems. In conventional RCGA, we used roulette wheel selection, tournament selection and the hybrid combination of both methods individually. Different combinations of cross over

Manuscript received July 27, 2004.

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techniques with the unique differential mutation are used along with the hybrid selection method in order to obtain the quality optimal solution of the hybrid system problem. We observed that, hybrid selection with hybrid cross over technique improves both the quality and optimal value of the fitness function of the control problem [3].

Particle swarm optimization (PSO) is one of the modern heuristic algorithms under the evolutionary algorithms (EA) and gained lots of attention in various power system applications [4]. It has been developed through simulation of simplified social models. We have analyzed the impact of inertia weight on the performance of PSO. When the inertia weight is high (say $I.W = 0.5$, $PSO -1$), the PSO converges faster and yields the solution faster but the optimal solution is not satisfactory. But at the same time when we reduce the inertia weight to a lower value of 0.1 ($PSO -2$), the PSO yields a better optimal solution but the convergence of the solution takes little more time. In order to get a compromise between optimal solution and convergence rate (or execution time), we defined a monotonic function, which decreases the inertia weight ($PSO -3$) linearly with the number of generations from 0.5 to 0.1. Now the optimal value is the lowest among all other PSO methods. The convergence rate is also improved over $PSO -2$ and slightly higher than $PSO -1$.

In this paper, we propose two-phase hybrid real coded genetic algorithms (HRCGA) with different forms of selection methods and crossover methods. The selection methods adopted in this paper are: Roulette wheel selection (RWS), Tournament selection (TS) and the hybrid combination of the both. The crossover operation is carried out with the hybrid combination of two different methods: Arithmetic crossover (AMXO), average crossover (ACXO), and dynamic mutation (DM) as a third genetic operator. In the first phase of the algorithm, real coded GA works and provides the potential near optimum solution, and the phase-2 of a search technique uses optimization by direct search and systematic reduction of the size of the search region. We compared our three proposed methods; each differs in selection method adopted, with that of conventional RCGA and PSO methods.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows: In section 2, the optimal control problem of a single stage hybrid manufacturing system is studied and formulated. The functional procedures of real coded GA and PSO are briefed in Section 3. Section 4 depicts the design of hybrid genetic operators for various RCGA methods, proposed HRCGA methods and the parameter selection for PSO algorithms. Section 5 gives the algorithmic and functional procedure for the two-phase HRCGA. The numerical example, the simulation results and the statistical analyses are given in section 6 and finally the discussions and conclusions are drawn in section 7.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION OF SINGLE STAGE HYBRID MANUFACTURING SYSTEM

The hybrid system framework with event-driven and time-driven dynamics is given in Fig 1.

Fig 1. Hybrid Frame work with time – driven and event-driven dynamics

The hybrid model of a single stage manufacturing hybrid system model is illustrated in Fig 2. A sequence of N jobs is assigned by an external source to arrive for processing at known times $0 \leq a_1 \leq \dots \leq a_N$. The jobs are denoted by C_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. The jobs are processed on first-come first-serve (FCFS) basis by a work-conserving and non-preemptive server. The processing time is $s(u_i)$, which is a function of a control variable u_i , and $s(u_i) \geq 0$.

Fig. 2. A single stage hybrid manufacturing system.

A job C_i is initially at some physical state ξ_i at time x_0 and subsequently evolves according to the time – driven dynamics of the hybrid system given in Eq.(1).

$$\dot{z}_i(t) = g(z_i, u_i, t), \quad z_i(x_0) = \xi_i \quad (1)$$

The event-driven dynamics is described by recursive non-linear equations (Max-plus equations) involving a maximum or a minimum operation, which is typically found in models of discrete event systems (DES). For the first-come first-serve (FCFS), nonpreemptive, single server example in figure 2, these dynamics is given by the standard Lindley equation of the form:

$$x_i = \max(x_{i-1}, a_i) + s(u_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

where x_i is the departure or completion time of i^{th} job.

From equations (1) and (2), it is clear that the choice of control u_i affects both the physical state z_i and the next temporal state x_i , and thus time-driven dynamics (1) and event-driven dynamics (2) justifying the hybrid nature of the system. According to [1], there are two alternative ways to view this hybrid system. The first is as a discrete event queuing system with time-driven dynamics evolving during processing in the server as shown in Fig 3.

Fig. 3. Typical Trajectory

The other viewpoint interprets the model as a switched system. In this framework, each job must be processed until it reaches a certain quality level denoted by Γ_i . That is, the processing time for each job is chosen such that :

$$s_i(u_i) = \min \left[t \geq 0; z_i(t_0) = \int_{t_0}^{t_0+t} g_i(\tau, u_i, \tau) d\tau + z(t_0) \in \Gamma_i \right] \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3 shows the evolution of the physical state as a function of time t . It is shown in the figure that the dynamics of the physical state experiences a “switch” when certain events occur. These events may be classified into two categories: uncontrolled (or exogenous) arrival events and controlled departure events. In Fig. 2, the first event is an exogenous arrival event at time a_1 . When the first job arrives at a_1 , the physical state starts to evaluate the time-driven dynamics until it reaches the departure time x_1 . Note that the first job completes before the second job arrives and hence there is an idle period, in which the server has no jobs to process. The physical state again begins evolving the time-driven dynamics at time a_2 (arrival of second job) until the second job completes at x_2 . Note, however, that the third job arrived before the second job was completed. So the third job is forced to wait in the queue until time x_2 . After the second job completes at x_2 the physical state begins to process the third job. As indicated in Fig.3, not only do the arrival time and departure time cause switching in the time-driven dynamics according to (1), but also the sequence in which these events occur is governed by the event-driven dynamics given in (2).

For the above single-stage framework defined by equations (1) and (2), the optimal control objective is to choose a control sequence $\{u_1, \dots, u_N\}$ to minimize an objective function of the form:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^N \{ \theta_i(u_i) + \phi_i(x_i) \}^{\eta} \quad (4)$$

Although, in general, the state variables z_i, \dots, z_N evolve continuously with time, minimizing (4) is an optimization problem in which the values of the state variables are considered only at the job completion times x_1, \dots, x_N . Since the stopping criterion in (3) is used to obtain the service times, a cost on the physical state $z_i(x_i)$ is unnecessary because the physical state of each completed job satisfies the quality objectives, i.e., $z_i(x_i) \in \Gamma_i$.

Generally speaking, u_i is a control variable affecting the processing time through $s_i = s(u_i)$ for extensions to cases with time-varying controls $u_i(t)$ over a service time. By assuming $s_i(\cdot)$ is either monotone increasing or monotone decreasing, given a control u_i , service time s_i can be determined from $s_i = s(u_i)$ and *vice versa*. For simplicity, let $s_i = u_i$ and the rest of the analysis is carried out with the notation u_i . Hence the optimal control problem, with $\eta = 1$, denoted by P is of the following form:

$$P: \min_{u_1, \dots, u_N} \left\{ J = \sum_{i=1}^N \{ \theta_i(u_i) + \phi_i(x_i) \} : u_i \geq 0, i=1, \dots, N \right\} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{subject to } x_i = \max(x_{i-1}, a_i) + s(u_i), \quad i=1, \dots, N \quad (6)$$

The optimal solution of P is denoted by u_i^* for $i=1, \dots, N$, and the corresponding departure time in equation (6) is denoted by x_i^* for $i=1, \dots, N$.

III. REVIEW OF REAL CODED GA AND PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION TECHNIQUES

The Genetic algorithm (GA) is a search technique based on the mechanics of natural genetics and survival of the fittest. GA is attractive and alternative tool for solving complex multi-modal optimization problems [5,6]. GA is unique as it operates from a rich database of many points simultaneously. Any carefully designed GA is only able to balance the exploration of the search effort, which means that an increase in the accuracy of a solution can only come at the sacrifice of convergent speed, and vice versa. It is unlikely that both of them can be improved simultaneously. Despite their superior search ability, GA still fails to meet the high expectations that theory predicts for the quality and efficiency of the solution. As widely accepted, a conventional GA (CGA) is only capable of identifying the high performance region at an affordable time and displaying inherent difficulties in performing local search for numerical applications [5-8].

A. REAL CODED GA:

To improve the final local tuning capabilities of a binary coded genetic algorithm, which is a must for high precision problems, new genetic operators have been introduced [6,9]. The main objective behind real coded GA implementations is to move the genetic algorithm closer to the problem space. For most applications of GAs to constrained optimization problems, the real coding is used to represent a solution to a given problem. Such coding is also known as floating-point representation, real number representation.

GAs start searching the solution by initialising a population of random candidates to the solution. Every individual in the population undergoes genetic evolution through crossover and mutation. The selection procedure is conducted based on the fitness of each individual. In this paper, the Roulette-wheel selection (RWS), Tournament selection (TS) and hybrid of both selection procedures are adopted in conjunction with the elitist strategy. By using elitist strategy, the best individual in each generation is ensured to be passed to the next generation.

The selection operator creates a new population by selecting individuals from the old populations, biased towards the best. The chromosomes, which produce the best optimal fitness, are selected for next generations. Crossover is the main genetic operator, which swaps chromosome parts between individuals. Crossover is not performed on every pair of individuals; its frequency being controlled by a crossover probability (P_c). The probability should have a larger value, typically, $P_c = 0.8$. The last operator is mutation and consists which changes a random part of string representing the individual. This operator must be used with some care, with low probability, typically P_m ranges from 0.01 to 0.1 for normal populations. The algorithm is repeated for several generations until one of the individuals of population converges to an optimal value or the required number of generations (max_gen) is reached. The high level behavior of GA can be depicted as in Table 1.

TABLE 1.
 A GENERAL GA PROCEDURE

Step 1:	Start
Step 2:	Generate (OLDPOP)
Step 3:	Repeat until limit
	Evaluate (OLDPOP)
	NEWPOP=Select (OLDPOP)
	Crossover (NEWPOP)
	Mutation (NEWPOP)
	OLDPOP=NEWPOP
Step 4:	End

Michalewicz [9] indicates that for real valued numerical optimization problems, floating-point representations outperform binary representations because they are more consistent, more precise, and lead to faster execution. For most applications of GAs to optimization problems, the real coding technique is used to represent a solution to a given problem. Hence, we use GA with real values in both conventional and hybrid, for solving the optimal control problem.

B. PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION:

Dr. Kennedy and Dr. Eberhart introduced particle swarm optimization in 1995 as an alternative to Genetic Algorithm (GA). The PSO technique has ever since turned out to be a competitor in the fields of numerical optimization. The evolutionary algorithms, EAs, (GA and EP) are search algorithms based on the simulated evolutionary process of natural selection, variation, and genetics. Both GA and EP can provide a near global solution [19]. EP differs from traditional GAs in two aspects: EP uses the real values, but not their coding as in traditional GAs, and EP relies primarily on mutation and selection, but not crossover, as in traditional GAs. Hence, considerable computation time may be saved in EP. Although GA and EP seem to be good methods to solve optimization problems, when applied to problems consisting of more number of local minima, the solutions obtained from both methods are just near global optimum ones [10].

PSO is similar to the other evolutionary algorithms in which the system is initialized with a population of random solutions. However, each potential solution is also assigned a randomized velocity, and the potential solutions corresponding to individuals. Generally, the PSO is characterized as a simple heuristic of well-balanced mechanism with flexibility to enhance and adapt to both global and local exploration abilities. It is a stochastic search technique with reduced memory requirement, computationally effective and easier to implement compared to other EAs. Also, PSO will not follow survival of the fittest, the principle of other EAs. PSO when compared to EP has very fast converging characteristics; however it has a slow fine-tuning ability of the solution. Also PSO has a more global searching ability at the beginning of the run and a local searching ability at the end of the run. Therefore, while solving problems with more local optima, there are more possibilities for the PSO to explore local optima at the end of the run [10,11].

Initial simulations were modified to incorporate nearest-neighbor velocity matching, eliminate ancillary variable, and accelerate movement. PSO is similar to genetic algorithm (GA) in that the system is initialized by a population of random solutions [11]. However, in PSO, each individual of the population, called particle, has an adaptable velocity,

according to which it moves over the search space. Each particle keeps track of its coordinates in hyperspace, which are associated with the solution (fitness) it has achieved so far [12]. This value is called personal best and is denoted by $pbest$. Additionally among these personal bests, there is only one, which has the best fitness. In a search space of D-dimensions, the i^{th} particle can be represented by a vector $X_i = X_1, X_2, \dots, X_D$. Similarly, the relevant velocity is represented by another D-dimensional vector $V_i = V_1, V_2, \dots, V_D$. The best among $pbest$ is called the global best, $gbest$.

$$V_i = wV_i + \rho_1 r_1 () (gbest - X_i) + \rho_2 r_2 () (pbest - X_i) \quad (7)$$

In equation (7), w is known as the inertia weight. The best-found position for the given particle is denoted by $pbest$ and $gbest$ is the best position known for all particles. The parameters ρ_1 and ρ_2 are set to constant values, which are normally given as 2 whereas r_1 and r_2 are two random values, uniformly distributed in $[0, 1]$. The position of each particle is updated every generation. This is done by adding the velocity vector to the position vector, as described in equation (8) below:

$$X_i = X_i + V_i \quad (8)$$

The PSO algorithm, which is used in this paper to solve the optimal control problem, is shown in table 2

TABLE 2.
PSO ALGORITHM

Step 1: Initialize

- Set index of Global best (Gbest index) = 1;

Step 2: Create population

- Randomize the positions and velocities for entire population
- Set the reference value of best position PB (i). Fitness
- Update velocity vector

Step 3: Calculate P (i). Fitness

- If P (i). Fitness < reference value of best position PB (i). Fitness
- Then Set new reference value of best position as P (i). Fitness
- If PB (i). Fitness < PB (GBestIndex). Fitness
- Then Set new GBestIndex = I

Step 4: Calculate the particle velocity and update the particle positions using the Eqns. (6) and (7)

Step 5: Repeat until Maximum number of generation is reached

The simplest version of PSO lets every individual move from a given point to a new one which is a weighted combination of the best position ever found (“nostalgia”), and of the individual’s best position, $pbest$. The choice of the PSO algorithm’s parameters (such as the group’s inertia) seems to be of utmost importance for the speed and efficiency of the algorithm [13 – 15]. Inertia weight plays an important role in the convergence of the optimal solution to a best optimal value as well as the execution time of the simulation run. The inertia weight controls the local and global exploration capabilities of PSO [10]. Large inertia weight enables the PSO to explore globally and small inertia weight enables it to explore locally. So the selection of inertia weight and maximum velocity allowed may be problem – dependent. The use of inertia weight, which typically decreases linearly, has provided improved performance in optimal control problems.

IV. SELECTION OF GENETIC OPERATORS AND PSO PARAMETERS

The main elements of a real coded GA include initial population, fitness function, genetic operators (selection, crossover and mutation), genetic structure, parameters (max_gen, P_c , and P_m) etc. For PSO, the parameters used in the algorithms are population size, population dimensions, maximum generations, inertia weight and search space.

A. Initial population

The initial populations are generated randomly. And the number of chromosomes generated per population is equal to the dimension of the optimal problem or equal to the number of jobs (N) involved in the main objective function. In this paper, the number of chromosomes generated per population (or the dimension of the optimal control problem) varies from 10 to 50.

B. Selection

Three different types of selection methods are used in this paper: Roulette wheel method, Tournament selection method, and the hybrid combinations with different proportions of roulette wheel and tournament selection methods.

1) Roulette Wheel Selection Method

Each individual in the population is assigned a space on the roulette wheel, which is proportional to the individual relative fitness. Individuals with the largest portion on the wheel have the greatest probability to be selected as parent generation for the next generation.

2) Tournament Selection Method

In tournament selection, a number $Tour$ of individuals are chosen randomly from the population and the best individual from this group is selected as a parent. This process is repeated to choose individuals often. These selected parents produce uniform offspring at random. The parameter for this method is the tournament size $Tour$. $Tour$ takes values ranging from $2 - N_{ind}$ (number of individuals in population).

3) Hybrid Selection Method

The hybrid selection method consists of the combination of both RWS and TS. We designed the hybrid selection operation as a single level hybrid selection method. In this technique, 50% of the population size adopts TS procedure where as the RWS procedure is used in the remaining 50% of the population size. For example, if we set population size as 20 then first 10 chromosomes follow TS method and the next 10 chromosomes follow RWS method.

C. Crossover

Crossover is the main genetic operator and consists of swapping chromosome parts between individuals. Crossover is not performed on every pair of individuals; its frequency being controlled by a crossover probability (P_c). There are several crossover methods available, but here we use hybrid combination of Arithmetic crossover method (AMXO), and Average Convex crossover (ACXO).

1) Arithmetic Crossover Method (AMXO)

The basic concept of this method is borrowed from the convex set theory [5,8,9]. Simple arithmetic operators are defined with the combination of two vectors (chromosomes) as follows:

$$x' = \lambda x + (1 - \lambda)y \quad (9)$$

$$x'' = (1 - \lambda)x + \lambda y \quad (10)$$

where λ is a uniformly distributed random variable between 0 and 1.

2) Average Convex Crossover Method (ACXO)

Generally, the weighted average of two vectors x_1 and x_2 are calculated as follows:

$$\lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 \quad (11)$$

If the multipliers are restricted as

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1, \quad \lambda_1 > 0, \quad \lambda_2 > 0 \quad (12)$$

The weighted form (11) is known as *convex combination*.

Similarly, arithmetic operators are defined as the combination of two chromosomes as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x'_1 &= \lambda_1 x_1 + \lambda_2 x_2 \\ x'_2 &= \lambda_1 x_2 + \lambda_2 x_1 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

According to the restriction of multipliers, it yields three kinds of crossovers, which can be called convex crossover, affine crossover, and linear crossover. Among the three methods, convex crossover may be the most commonly used method [5]. When restricting $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = 0.5$, it yields a special case, which is called as *Average convex crossover* by Davis or *Intermediate crossover* by Schwefel [9].

3) Hybrid Crossover Methods

In this paper we designed four hybrid crossover methods from the above said two crossover operations (AMXO and ACXO). In the hybrid cross-over method, 50% of the population size adopts AMXO procedure where as the ACXO procedure is used in the remaining 50% of the population size. We used some other crossover methods like direction based crossover, single point crossover but the above said two methods outperform all the other, hence we choose AMXO and ACXO for hybrid method.

D. Mutation

The final genetic operator is Mutation. It can create a new genetic material in the population to maintain the population's diversity. It is nothing but changing a random part of string representing the individual. In this paper, dynamic mutation is used.

1) Dynamic Mutation

Michalewicz [9] proposed this mutation operator, also known as non-uniform mutation. It is designed for fine-tuning capabilities aimed at achieving high precision. For a given parent x , the element x_k is randomly selected from the following two possible choices:

$$\begin{aligned} x'_k &= x_k + \Delta(t, x_k^U - x_k) \\ \text{or } x'_k &= x_k + \Delta(t, x_k - x_k^L) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The function $\Delta(t, dx)$ returns a value in the range $[0, dx]$ such that the value of $\Delta(t, dx)$ approaches 0 as t increases. This property causes the operator to search the space uniformly initially (when t is small) and very locally at later stages. The function $\Delta(t, dx)$ is given as follows:

$$\Delta(t, dx) = dx \cdot r \cdot \left(1 - \frac{t}{T}\right)^d \quad (15)$$

where r is a random number from $(0,1)$, T is the maximal generation number and d is a parameter determining the degree of non-uniformity (usually assumed as 2 or 3).

E. Elitism

In order to enrich the future generations with specific genetic information of the parent with best fitness from the current generations, that particular parent with the best fitness is preserved in the next generations. This method of preserving the elite parent is called *elitism*. This property is incorporated in our proposed algorithms.

F. Population Size

From the earlier research, done by Shi, in 1998, it is proved that the performance of the standard algorithm is not sensitive to the population size. Based on these results the population size in the experiments was fixed at 20 particles in order to keep the computational requirements low. The size of the population will affect the convergence of the solution. Hence we set population size to 20 in our work.

G. Search Space

The range in which the algorithm computes the optimal control variables is called search space. The algorithm will search for the optimal solution in the search space which is between 0 and 1. When any of the optimal control value of any particle exceeds the searching space, the value will be reinitialized. In this paper the lower boundary is set to zero (0) and the upper boundary to one (1).

H. Dimension

The dimension is the number of independent variables, which is identical to the number of jobs considered for processing in the hybrid system framework. In this paper, the dimension of the optimal control problem varies between 10 and 50.

I. Max Generations

This refers to the maximum number of generations allowed for the fitness value to converge with the optimal solution. We set 1000 generations for the simulation.

J. Inertia Weight

When the inertia weight is high (>0.7), the convergence rate is faster but the optimal solution is not so optimal, but for the lower value of inertia weight (<0.7), the convergence rate is slower but the optimal solution is better. The monotonically decreasing inertia weight from a higher value to a lower value yields the better optimal solution with faster convergence. We used all three categories in our algorithms to compare the effect of inertia weight. In the monotonically decreasing inertia weight technique, the first generation is simulated with

the higher value of inertia weight say 0.7, and the last generations with lower inertia weight 0.3. So from generation 1 to 1000, the inertia weight also decreases from 0.7 to 0.3.

K. Solution acceleration technique

The convergence of the real coded GA can be accelerated greatly by assuming that the best solution in the population is closest to the global optimum. If it is true, then searching the solution space in this neighborhood will produce solutions closer to the global optimum. This can be accomplished by re-mapping the population after each competition stage in the GA algorithm so that all solutions are moved a random distance towards the best solution at that generation. This results in more solutions in the neighborhood of the minimum and hence allows a more thorough search of its surrounds [16].

Mathematically, the solution acceleration technique, which is given in (16), can be described as follows:

$$x' = x_b + r(x_b - x) \quad (16)$$

where x_b = best solution vector (best individual) in the population
 x = solution vector (individual) to be re-mapped
 x' = re-mapped solution vector
 r = uniformly distributed random number between 0 and 1.

V. TWO PHASE HYBRID GENETIC ALGORITHM (HRCGA):

The major difference that hybrid GAs can make regarding performance enhancement is that they can provide an acceptable solution within a relatively short time. In general, local search techniques have the advantage of solving the problem quickly, though their results are very much dependent on the initial starting point; therefore, they can easily be trapped in a local optimum. On the other hand, genetic algorithm samples a large search space, climbs many peaks in parallel, and is likely to lead the search towards the most promising area. However, a GA faces difficulties in a fine-tuning of local search; it spends most of the time competing between different hills, rather than improving the solution along a single hill that the optimal point locates. Hence, if one can make use of the advantages of both the local and GA techniques, one can improve the search algorithm both effectively and efficiently [6, 9, and 17].

The proposed hybrid GA combines a standard real coded GA and the phase - 2 of conventional search technique. Real coded GA takes the place of the phase - 1 of the search [6, 9],

providing the potential near optimum solution, and the phase - 2 of a search technique using optimization by direct search and systematic reduction in size of the search region [18]. Phase - 2 algorithm is applied to rapidly generate a precise solution under the assumption that the evolutionary search has generated a solution near the global optimum.

A. Phase - 1 Algorithm

Real coded GA is implemented as follows:

1) A population of N_p trail solutions is initialized. Each solution is taken as a real valued vector with their dimensions corresponding to the number of variables. The initial components of \mathbf{x} are selected in accordance with a uniform distribution ranging between 0 and 1.

2) The fitness score for each solution vector \mathbf{x} is evaluated using Eq. 4, after converting each solution vector into corresponding problem variables \mathbf{x}_a using upper and lower bound vectors.

3) Three different (RWS, TS and Hybrid) selection method are used individually to produce N_p offspring from parents.

4) Hybrid crossover (combination of Arithmetic crossover and Average crossover), non-uniform mutation operators and solution acceleration technique are applied to offspring to generate next generation parents.

5) The algorithm proceeds to step 2, unless the best solution does not change for a pre - specified interval of generations. Specifically, the phase - 1 of the hybrid algorithm stops if the following condition of eqn.17 is satisfied: for the feasible best solution vector at generation t , $\mathbf{x}[t]$, and generation $t-1$, $\mathbf{x}[t-1]$,

$$\left(\frac{|x_j[t] - x_j[t-1]|}{|x_j[t]|} \right) \leq \rho l \quad (17)$$

for a sufficiently small positive value ρl , and for all j , for successive $Ng1$ generations.

B. Phase - 2 Algorithm

After the phase - 1 is halted, satisfying the halting condition described in the previous section, optimization by direct search and systematic reduction in size of the search region method is employed in the phase - 2. In the light of the solution accuracy, the success rate, and the computation time, the best solution vector obtained from the phase - 1 is used as an initial point for the phase - 2.

The optimization procedure based on direct search and systematic reduction in search region is found effective in solving various problems in the field of non-linear

programming. This procedure handles either inequality or equality constraints or the feasible region does not have to be convex and no approximations or auxiliary variables are required. The most attractive features are the ease of setting up the problem on the computer, speed in obtaining the optimum and reliability of the results. For problems where more than one local optimum can occur, this method is especially useful [18]. This direct search optimization procedure is implemented as follows:

1. The best solution vector obtained from the phase - 1 of the hybrid algorithm is used as an initial point $x(0)$ for phase - 2 and an initial range vector is defined as

$$R(0) = RMF * Range \quad (18)$$

where *Range* is defined as the difference between the upper and lower bound vectors of \mathbf{x} and *RMF* is the range multiplication factor. The *RMF* value varies between 0 and 1. In general, the value of *RMF* may be selected around 0.5 as discussed in simulation results section.

2. Generate N_s trail solution vectors around $x(0)$ using following relationship,

$$x_i = x(0) + R(0) * rand(1, n) \quad (19)$$

where x_i is i^{th} trail solution vector, $*$ represents element-by-element multiplication operation and $rand(1, n)$ is a random vector, whose elements value varies from 0 to 1.

3. For each feasible trail solution vector find the objective function value using eqn.1 and find the trail solution set, which minimizes $f(\mathbf{x})$ and equate it to $x(0)$.

$$x(0) = x_{Best} \quad (20)$$

where x_{best} is the trail solution set with minimum $f(\mathbf{x})$ for minimization problems and maximum $f(\mathbf{x})$ for maximization problems.

4. Reduce the range by an amount given by

$$R(0) = R(0) * (1 - \beta) \quad (21)$$

where β is the range reduction factor, whose typical value is 0.02 or 0.05.

5. The algorithm proceeds to step2, unless the best solution does not change for a pre - specified interval of iterations or maximum number of iterations reached.

The main reason for the success of this algorithm lies in its local search ability. Since the values for the variables are always chosen around the best point determined in the previous iteration, there is a more likelihood of convergence to the optimum solution. In contrast, GAs spends most of the time competing between different hills, rather than improving the solution along a single hill that the optimal point locates.

VI. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE, SIMULATION RESULTS AND STATISTICAL ANALYSES

In order to compare the validity and usefulness of the proposed hybrid real coded GA method, we considered the optimal control problem from equations (5) and (6) with the following functions:

$$\theta_i(u_i) = \frac{2}{u_i}, \quad \phi(x_i) = 3 * x_i \text{ and } \eta = 1.5 \quad (22)$$

Now equation (5) becomes,

$$\min_{u_1, \dots, u_N} \left\{ J = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{2}{u_i} + 3x_i \right)^{1.5} \right\} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{subject to } x_i = \max(x_{i-1}, a_i) + u_i \quad (24)$$

The optimal controls (u_i) and cost or fitness (J) for the objective function given in equation (22) are computed with the following parameter settings.

The dimension or the number of jobs involved in the objective function $N = (10, 20, 30, 40, 50)$, Crossover probability $P_c = 0.8$ and Probability of mutation $P_m = 0.01$. The maximum number of generations is set as 1000 with the population size of 20.

The arrival sequence (a_i for $i = 1$ to N) for $N = (10, 20, 30, 40, 50)$, are obtained from the following algorithm given in Table 3.

TABLE 3.
ARRIVAL SEQUENCE FOR HYBRID SYSTEMS.

ab(1) = 0.3
ab(2) = 0.5
ab(3) = 0.7
ab(4) = 1
For bb = 1 To N/4
For aa = 1 To 4
ab(aa + 4 * bb) = ab(aa) + 1 * bb
Next aa
Next bb
For i = 1 To N
a(i) = ab(i)
Next i

The number of arrival times, (a_i for $i = 1$ to N) is taken according to the dimension of the problem, i.e, the number of jobs (N) considered for processing.

We solved the optimal control problem considered in this section, which is given in equations (22 - 24) using three proposed 2 phase hybrid GA methods. The proposed algorithm adopts roulette wheel selection and the second adopts tournament selection and the third provides hybrid of both selection techniques.

We used a hybrid cross over technique, with arithmetic cross-over (AMXO) and average cross – over (ACXO) methods. The dynamic mutation is the unique choice of mutation operation.

In order to compare the efficacy and validity, and to prove the betterment of the proposed two- phase HRCGA method, we solved the same optimal problem described in this section through three PSO techniques (differs from each other with inertia weight), and three conventional RCGA methods (differs from each other with the selection procedure adopted).

All the above nine methods, given in Table (4), are simulated 1000 times at different intervals of time, and their statistical analyses are obtained. The *Mean or average* of the fitness value obtained in 1000 runs and their *Standard Deviation (SD)* are the basic statistical tests. From these two, we calculated the *Co-efficient of Variance (CV)*, which is the ratio of standard deviation to Mean. The fourth statistical test is *Average Deviation (AVEDEV)*, which will give the average of the absolute deviation of the fitness values from their *mean*, which are taken in 1000 simulation runs. The graphical comparisons of standard deviation and Average deviation of the fitness value over 1000 runs for $N = 10$ to 50 are shown in Fig 8(a-e). Added to these basic analyses, *hypothesis t – test and analysis of variance (ANOVA)* test also were carried out to validate the efficacy of all the nine methods. These statistics analysis are presented in Tables 5 – 9. The graphical analyses are done through Box plot, which are shown in Figures 5 (a-e).

A box plot, which is shown in Figure 4, provides an excellent visual summary of many important aspects of a distribution. The box stretches from the lower hinge (defined as the 25th percentile) to the upper hinge (the 75th percentile) and therefore contains the middle half of the scores in the distribution. The median is shown as a line across the box. Therefore 1/4 of the distribution is between this line and the top of the box and 1/4 of the distribution is between this line and the bottom of the box.

The n^{th} percentile of a distribution of values is defined as the cumulative probability in percent, that is the value that bounds the $n\%$ of values below and the $(100-n)\%$ above it. In this report the box plot consists of a plot where 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles are drawn. Looking at the box plot the general features of the distribution can be evinced. For instance, if all

Figure 4. A simple Box Plot

the percentiles of the model that are drawn in the box plot are lower than the percentiles of the corresponding measurements. It means that the lower 75 % of the predictions is lower than the lower 75 % of measurements. This might probably correspond to a modeled distribution everywhere lower than the measured one or, less likely, to a model distribution much more peaked in the 25 (or less) % of higher values.

Table 4 gives the description of all the nine methods considered in this paper. The methods are classified according to the optimization algorithm used to compute the optimal control of the objective function. The above programmes were developed both in MATLAB 6.1 and Visual Basic 5.0 software packages.

For the purpose of comparison, we have considered our earlier work on particle swarm optimization (PSO) and real coded GA. All the methods are analyzed through hypothesis test and finally by fitness regulation of the other methods over the best method among all the nine methods.

TABLE 4.
 VARIOUS OF THE EVOLUTIONARY OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHMS

S.No.	Type of EA	Methods	Description
1	Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)	PSO - 1	PSO with high inertia weight (I.W = 0.7)
		PSO - 2	PSO with low inertia weight (I.W = 0.3)
		PSO - 3	PSO with monotonically decreasing inertia weight from 0.7 to 0.3
2	Conventional Real coded Genetic Algorithm (C RCGA)	RCGA_RWS	RCGA with roulette wheel selection, dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over
		RCGA_TS	RCGA with Tournament selection, dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over
		RCGA_HGO	RCGA with hybrid selection (RWS + TS), dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over
3	Proposed 2 phase Hybrid Real coded Genetic Algorithm (HRCGA)	HRCGA_RWS	Proposed 2 phase HRCGA with roulette wheel selection dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over
		HRCGA_TS	Proposed 2 phase HRCGA with Tournament selection, dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over
		HRCGA_HGO	Proposed 2 phase HRCGA with hybrid selection, dynamic mutation and hybrid cross over

TABLE 5.
 STATISTIC ANALYSES OF FITNESS VALUE FOR N = 10

Method No.	Statistical Test	Average	SD	CV	AVEDEV	T-TEST for N = 10		
						Method Nos.	P Value	Best Method
1	PSO - 1	423.54124	0.56570	0.00134	0.38957			
2	PSO - 2	414.37031	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	1 & 2	1.0000	2
3	PSO - 3	414.37031	0.00000	0.00000	0.00000	2 & 3	0.9994	2
4	RCGA_RWS	423.02521	0.48518	0.00115	0.36491	2 & 4	0.0000	2
5	RCGA_TS	415.97974	0.33882	0.00081	0.29353	2 & 5	0.0000	2
6	RCGA_HGO	415.37357	0.22958	0.00055	0.16616	2 & 6	0.0000	2
7	HRCGA_RWS	414.37030	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	2 & 7	0.0000	2
8	HRCGA_TS	414.37030	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	2 & 8	1.0000	8
9	HRCGA_HGO	414.37030	0.00001	0.00000	0.00000	8 & 9	0.9998	9

Fig 5(a) ANOVA t – test for N = 10

Fig 6(a) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for PSO algorithms for N = 10

Fig 7(a) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for RCGA algorithms for N = 10

Fig 8(a) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for proposed HRCGA algorithms for N = 10

TABLE 6.
 STATISTIC ANALYSES OF FITNESS VALUE FOR N = 20

Method No.	Statistical Test	Average	SD	CV	AVEDEV	T-TEST for N = 20		
						Method Nos.	P Value	Best Method
1	PSO - 1	1390.95048	0.39445	0.00028	0.31133	1 & 2	1.0000	2
2	PSO - 2	1331.29258	0.28106	0.00021	0.24329	2 & 3	0.9994	3
3	PSO - 3	1331.08606	0.17978	0.00014	0.14429	3 & 4	0.0000	3
4	RCGA_RWS	1381.55553	0.69174	0.00050	0.39690	3 & 5	0.0000	3
5	RCGA_TS	1361.19747	0.79200	0.00058	0.63184	3 & 6	0.0000	3
6	RCGA_HGO	1356.81273	0.41574	0.00031	0.31490	3 & 7	0.0000	3
7	HRCGA_RWS	1331.60000	0.29361	0.00022	0.23853	3 & 8	1.0000	8
8	HRCGA_TS	1330.93667	0.05561	0.00004	0.05137	8 & 9	0.7625	9
9	HRCGA_HGO	1330.92667	0.05208	0.00004	0.04185			

Fig 5(b) ANOVA t – test for N = 20

Fig 6(b) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for PSO algorithms for N = 20

Fig 7(b) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for RCGA algorithms for N = 20

Fig 8(b) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for proposed HRCGA algorithms for N = 20

TABLE 7.
 STATISTIC ANALYSES OF FITNESS VALUE FOR N = 30

Method No.	Statistical Test	Average	SD	CV	AVEDEV	T-TEST for N=30		
						Method Nos.	P Value	Best Method
1	PSO - 1	2906.40568	1.08340	0.00037	0.87947	1 & 2	1.0000	2
2	PSO - 2	2805.24470	0.21571	0.00008	0.14058	2 & 3	0.8007	3
3	PSO - 3	2804.79883	0.14538	0.00005	0.10923	3 & 4	0.0000	3
4	RCGA_RWS	2898.92640	0.99552	0.00034	0.81273	3 & 5	0.0000	3
5	RCGA_TS	2880.37656	0.88922	0.00031	0.63029	3 & 6	0.0000	3
6	RCGA_HGO	2858.79713	0.79978	0.00028	0.51809	3 & 7	0.0000	3
7	HRCGA_RWS	2807.00833	0.09841	0.00004	0.05982	3 & 8	1.0000	8
8	HRCGA_TS	2804.09877	0.06939	0.00002	0.06057	8 & 9	1.0000	9
9	HRCGA_HGO	2803.99745	0.05465	0.00002	0.03682			

Fig 5(c) ANOVA t – test for N = 30

Fig 6(c) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for PSO algorithms for N = 30

Fig 7(c) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for RCGA algorithms for N = 30

Fig 8(c) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for proposed HRCGA algorithms for N = 30

TABLE 8.
 STATISTIC ANALYSES OF FITNESS VALUE FOR N = 40

Method No.	Statistical Test	Average	SD	CV	AVEDEV	T-TEST for N=40		
						Method Nos.	P Value	Best Method
1	PSO - 1	5015.96607	1.12387	0.00022	0.91158	1 & 2	1.0000	2
2	PSO - 2	4915.58055	0.65593	0.00011	0.50865	2 & 3	0.9829	3
3	PSO - 3	4915.45251	0.62702	0.00013	0.50056	3 & 4	0.0000	3
4	RCGA_RWS	5006.66472	0.97196	0.00019	0.76077	3 & 5	0.0000	3
5	RCGA_TS	4987.95148	0.94147	0.00019	0.67175	3 & 6	0.0000	3
6	RCGA_HGO	4986.87711	0.88543	0.00018	0.61804	3 & 7	0.0000	3
7	HRCGA_RWS	4924.22750	0.65949	0.00013	0.54541	3 & 8	1.0000	8
8	HRCGA_TS	4914.47004	0.53144	0.00011	0.43363	8 & 9	0.9934	9
9	HRCGA_HGO	4913.15394	0.52451	0.00011	0.39546			

Fig 5(d) ANOVA t – test for N = 40

Fig 6(d) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for PSO algorithms for N = 40

Fig 7(d) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for RCGA algorithms for N = 40

Fig 8 (d) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for proposed HRCGA algorithms for N = 40

TABLE 9.
 STATISTIC ANALYSES OF FITNESS VALUE FOR N = 50

Method No.	Statistical Test	Average	SD	CV	AVEDEV	T-TEST for N=50		
						Method Nos.	P Value	Best Method
1	PSO - 1	7782.94335	0.90988	0.00012	0.71395	1 & 2	1.0000	2
2	PSO - 2	7744.00010	0.49792	0.00006	0.38174	2 & 3	0.9830	3
3	PSO - 3	7743.72344	0.49009	0.00006	0.37372	3 & 4	0.0000	3
4	RCGA_RWS	7761.02276	1.26549	0.00016	1.00445	3 & 5	0.0000	3
5	RCGA_TS	7759.42501	1.18389	0.00015	0.93502	3 & 6	0.0000	3
6	RCGA_HGO	7748.89319	0.99000	0.00013	0.71907	3 & 7	0.0000	3
7	HRCGA_RWS	7744.62652	0.50900	0.00007	0.38848	3 & 8	1.0000	8
8	HRCGA_TS	7730.98000	0.49158	0.00006	0.37883	8 & 9	0.9937	9
9	HRCGA_HGO	7729.97667	0.42563	0.00006	0.28133			

Fig 5(e) ANOVA t – test for N = 50

Fig 6(e) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for PSO algorithms for N = 50

Fig 7(e) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for RCGA algorithms for N = 50

Fig 8(e) Convergence of Fitness value over generations for proposed HRCGA algorithms for N = 50

Fig 9(a) Comparison of SD and AVEDEV for N = 10

Fig 9(b) Comparison of SD and AVEDEV for N = 20

Fig 9(c) Comparison of SD and AVEDEV for N = 30

Fig 9(d) Comparison of SD and AVEDEV for N = 40

Fig 9(e) Comparison of SD and AVEDEV for N = 50

Fig 10. Percentage of Fitness value Regulation of other methods from the best proposed method (HRCGA_HGO)

Fitness Regulation:

The percentage of deviation of the average fitness value for the other eight methods from the best among nine methods are calculated using equation (25), for analyzing the better performance of the proposed algorithm. They are presented in Table 10.

$$[\% \text{ of Deviation of the fitness value}] = \left(\frac{\text{Fitness of HRCGA_HGO} - \text{Fitness of other methods}}{\text{Fitness of HRCGA_HGO}} \right) \times 100 \quad (25)$$

TABLE 10.
 THE FITNESS VALUE REGULATION OF OTHER METHODS FROM THE BEST-PROPOSED METHOD (HRCGA_HGO)

No .of Jobs	PSO - 1	PSO - 2	PSO - 3	RCGA_RWS	RCGA_TS	RCGA_HGO	HRCGA_RWS	HRCGA_TS
10	-2.2132	0.0000	0.0000	-2.0887	-0.3884	-0.2421	0.0000	0.0000
20	-4.5099	-0.0275	-0.0120	-3.8040	-2.2744	-1.9450	-0.0506	-0.0008
30	-3.6522	-0.0445	-0.0286	-3.3855	-2.7239	-1.9543	-0.1074	-0.0036
40	-1.1640	-0.0494	-0.0468	-1.9033	-1.5224	-1.5005	-0.2254	-0.0268
50	-0.6852	-0.1814	-0.1778	-0.4016	-0.3810	-0.2447	-0.1895	-0.0039

VII DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, new two-phase hybrid real coded genetic algorithms with hybrid genetic operators are proposed. This algorithm (2-phase HRCGA) can out perform conventional genetic algorithms and PSO in the sense that hybrid GAs make it possible to improve both the quality of the solution and reduce the computing expenses. The phase -1 uses standard real coded genetic algorithm, while optimization by direct search with systematic reduction in the size of the search region is employed in the phase - 2. This hybrid algorithm handles either inequality or equality constraints and the feasible region does not have to be convex and gradient or other auxiliary information's are not required. In order to prove the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm, this method is applied to typical constrained optimization function. The results obtained are compared with other methods. The outcome of the study clearly demonstrates the effectiveness and robustness that a hybrid genetic algorithm (HGA) can achieve over a conventional RCGA and PSO algorithms. From the results, it is very clear that hybrid GA not only improves the success rate but also decreases the number function evaluations and computation time.

In this paper, three different evolutionary algorithms are considered. Three algorithms for each of these three methods, a total of nine methods are considered. In order to compare the validity and usefulness of the proposed hybrid real coded GA method with the other evolutionary methods, 1000 simulated results for each method are taken at different timings. In order to hasten the convergence in hybrid real coded GA's solution and the population dimension (*Pop_Size*), maximum of number of generation (*max_gen*), are set to 20 and 1000 respectively. The performance of different algorithms is compared with respect to the solution accuracy in the fitness, the standard deviations, co-efficient variance, average deviation, ANOVA t-test, and the percentage of deviation in the fitness from the proposed best method.

From the results stated in Table 5 – 9, it is obvious that the method - 9 (*HRCGA_HGO*) is best followed by method - 8 (*HRCGA_TS*). This clearly establishes the fact that hybrid selections together with hybrid crossover methods yield better solutions. This is the most significant outcome of the experiments performed. These combinations have been shown to work efficiently with regard to an optimal control problem here but it is believed that these might be equally efficient with regard to all other problems where hybrid real coded GA can be used.

A. From the ANOVA test and t – test:

The hypothesis t – Test and ANOVA test are also carried out to prove the best method among all the nine methods considered here, and their P-values are also recorded. The ANOVA test results are drawn using Box plots. From the box plot figures, which are given in Fig 5 (a-e), it is obvious that method - 9 (*HRCGA_HGO*) gives the best results among all other methods. This clearly indicates that the hybrid selection with the hybrid combination of AMXO and ACXO gives the best results.

B. From the convergence of fitness graphs:

Fig. 6 (a-e), Fig 7(a-e), and Fig 8(a-e) show the convergence characteristics of PSO, real coded and hybrid real coded genetic algorithms respectively for number of jobs $N = 10, 20, 30, 40$ and 50 . It is clearly seen from the graphs that the proposed two phase HRCGA methods converge very earlier, around generation 200, which is not so in other methods (see Fig 7(a-e)). PSO methods convergences faster but only for less number of jobs. For higher number of jobs, PSO also takes more number of generations to converge with the final optimal value (see Fig 5(a-e)). In the case of the conventional RCGA methods (Fig 6(a-e)), the convergences of fitness value with the optimal value take more number of generations, which will in turn take longer computation time. It clearly shows the

inefficiency of real coded GA in fine local tuning. If, for the entire search, real coded GA were employed then there would be a mere wastage of amount computation time without any change in solution vector and objective function value. Since the two phase HRCGA method converges at less number of generations, this algorithm takes less computation time in comparison to the other methods in order to obtain the optimal solution.

C. From the SD and Average dev. Graph:

It is very obvious that the standard deviation and average deviations are the quality measures of statistical analyses. In order to obtain the optimal value of the fitness function, the optimization algorithms were run 1000 times in different intervals of time. If the algorithm gives nearly same solution in each and every run, then we can say that the algorithm is consistent and stable for solving the optimal control problem.

In order to prove the consistency and stability on the optimal solution, standard deviations and average deviations of the fitness value are taken through the 1000 simulated runs. If the standard deviation is very minimum, it implies that the solution obtained in each of 1000 runs are more or less equal and the differences between the solutions over each runs are less. Therefore, if an algorithm provides very low standard deviation then it can be concluded that the algorithm is consistent. From Fig 8 (a-e), it is observed that method 9 provides a very low standard deviation among all other methods.

The average deviation gives the measure of how much the solution is deviated from the average (mean) value of the fitness. For the algorithm to be on best side, it should produce a very low average deviation. From Fig 8 (a-e), it is very clearly seen that the 9th method gives a very low average deviation. Hence we strongly conclude that the 9th method is the best among the others.

D. From the Fitness regulation:

The same conclusions can also be drawn from Table 10, where percentage of deviations of fitness values, called as fitness regulation, were obtained through methods 1 to 8 from the proposed best method; method - 9 (HRCGA_HGO) is recorded. For smaller number of jobs, method - 8 (HRCGA_TS) and method - 3 (PSO-3) also yield the optimum value but when the numbers of jobs increase they are differ from method - 9.

The graphical representation of this fitness regulation is shown in Fig 10. The negative values of this fitness regulation indicate that methods 1 – 8 are inferior to

method - 9. The zero fitness regulation for the particular methods indicate that the optimum value is same with the proposed best method - 9. Based on this, it can be concluded that the hybrid real coded GA with the hybrid genetic operators gives the best optimal value over the other methods.

In other words, the superior performance of the hybrid combinations of the genetic operators for two phase hybrid real coded genetic algorithms has been clearly established in this paper.

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